

A Workloads and Configuration Options

We provide the full list of selected configuration options used in our case study for the three subject systems: LLVM (Table 2 on page 23), SQLITE (Table 4 on page 24), and APACHE (Table 3 on page 23). We also provide the full list of workloads used in our case study for the three subject systems in Table 5 on page 24.

Table 2. Selected configuration options for LLVM

Index	Parameter	Value
1	inline	{on, off}
2	openmpopt	{on, off}
3	mldst-motion	{on, off}
4	gvn	{on, off}
5	jump-threading	{on, off}
6	correlated-propagation	{on, off}
7	elim-avail-extern	{on, off}
8	tailcallelim	{on, off}
9	constmerge	{on, off}
10	dse	{on, off}
11	slp-vectorizer	{on, off}
12	callsite-splitting	{on, off}
13	argpromotion	{on, off}
14	aggressive-instcombine	{on, off}
15	polly-simplify	{on, off}
16	polly-dce	{on, off}
17	polly-optree	{on, off}
18	polly-delicm	{on, off}
19	polly-opt-isl	{on, off}
20	polly-prune-unprofitable	{on, off}

Table 3. Selected configuration options for APACHE

Index	Parameter	Value
1	AcceptFilter	{nntp, http}
2	KeepAlive	{on, off}
3	KeepAliveTimeout	{1, ..., 300}
4	MaxKeepAliveRequests	{1, ..., 2 ¹⁰ }
5	TimeOut	{1, ..., 300}
6	MaxConnectionsPerChild	{1, ..., 1,000}
7	MaxMemFree	{2 ¹⁰ , ..., 2 ²⁰ }
8	MaxRequestWorkers	{100, ..., 3,000}
9	MaxSpareThreads	{50, ..., 500}
10	MinSpareThreads	{20, ..., 250}
11	SendBufferSize	{2 ¹⁰ , ..., 2 ¹⁶ }
12	ServerLimit	{100, ..., 3,000}
13	StartServers	{1, ..., 10}
14	ThreadLimit	{10, ..., 200}
15	ThreadsPerChild	{10, ..., 200}

Table 4. Selected configuration options for SQLite

Index	Parameter	Value
1	SQLITE_SECURE_DELETE	{on, off}
2	SQLITE_TEMP_STORE	{0, 1, 2, 3}
3	SQLITE_ENABLE_AUTO_WRITE	{on, off}
4	SQLITE_ENABLE_STAT3	{on, off}
5	SQLITE_DISABLE_LFS	{on, off}
6	SQLITE_OMIT_AUTO_INDEX	{on, off}
7	SQLITE_OMIT_BETWEEN_OPT	{on, off}
8	SQLITE_OMIT_BTREECOUNT	{on, off}
9	SQLITE_OMIT_LIKE_OPT	{on, off}
10	SQLITE_OMIT_LOOKASIDE	{on, off}
11	SQLITE_OMIT_OR_OPT	{on, off}
12	SQLITE_OMIT_QUICKBALANCE	{on, off}
13	SQLITE_OMIT_SHARED_CACHE	{on, off}
14	CacheSize	{1, ..., 10, 240}
15	AutoVacuumON	{0, 1, 2}
16	ExclusiveLock	{on, off}
17	PageSize	{1, ..., 10, 240}
18	Wal	{on, off}

Table 5. Lookup table of settings of different workloads for three configurable software systems.

\mathcal{W}	LLVM	SQLITE		APACHE	
Index	program_name	num	value_size	requests	concurrency
1	2mm	10	100	50	50
2	3mm	10	1,000	100	100
3	atax	10	10,000	100	100
4	correlation	10	30,000	200	200
5	covariance	100	100	250	250
6	deriche	100	100	300	300
7	doitgen	100	1,000	400	400
8	fdtd2d	100	10,000	500	500
9	gemm	100	30,000	1,000	100
10	symm	1,000	10		
11	syr2k				
12	syrk				
13	trmm				